

Enhanced SAR-Based Shoreline Extraction in Microtidal Beaches Through Improved Preprocessing of Sentinel-1 and TerraSAR-X Data

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Abstract—Shoreline extraction from synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery has been increasingly explored due to its all-weather, day-and-night observation capabilities. In this study, a robust methodology for automatic shoreline detection was developed and validated using SAR data from Sentinel-1 (S1, 20 images) and TerraSAR-X (TSX, two images). SAR images acquired over four microtidal Mediterranean sandy and gravel beaches were processed using a multistep workflow that included preprocessing, noise reduction, land–sea segmentation by clustering or thresholding methods, shoreline extraction, and outlier detection techniques. The accuracy of the SAR-derived shorelines was evaluated against reference ones obtained from high-resolution aerial orthomosaics or PlanetScope imagery. The results of the S1 analyses demonstrated excellent accuracy and stability for gravel beaches [approximately 6 m of mean absolute deviation (MAD)], and for sandy beaches (approximately 7 m of MAD), in this latter case with significant variations observed between the two sites. In a comparative assessment, TSX data achieved higher accuracy in terms of MAD (2.5 m) compared to S1 (6.5 m) in the same context, but only in the image with good meteorological conditions (no differences were obtained in the other date). In general, the use of the block-matching and 3-D filtering filter significantly improved image quality, reducing noise artifacts and enhancing the contrast between land and sea, especially in not-perfect meteorological conditions, which usually influenced SAR-derived shoreline accuracy. Using three classes in the classification also produced better results, and outlier detection played a minor role. Overall, this study demonstrates that the innovative integration of advanced image processing techniques and classification algorithms significantly enhances the reliability of SAR-based shoreline detection. The findings underscore the potential of SAR imagery as a valuable tool for coastal monitoring. Achieving an accuracy close to that obtainable with multispectral data, shoreline extracted from SAR

could be successfully used in areas with frequent cloud cover or limited optical data availability.

Index Terms—Remote sensing, satellite imagery, Sentinel-1 (S1), shoreline extraction, TerraSAR-X (TSX).

NOMENCLATURE

ASC	Ascending mode orbit.
DESC	Descending mode orbit.
ESA	European Space Agency.
FNG	Feniglia beach.
GEE	Google Earth engine.
GMM	Gaussian mixture model.
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system.
GRD	Ground range distance.
IW	Interferometric wide swath.
MAD	Mean absolute distance.
ML	Machine learning.
MRJ	Playa de Marjal.
PLN	PlanetScope.
RDC	Ribera de Cabanes.
SAR	Synthetic aperture radar.
SLD	Southern Llobregat Delta beach.
SWI	SARWI.
S1	Sentinel-1.
S2	Sentinel-2.
TSX	TerraSAR-X.

I. INTRODUCTION

COASTAL zones are among Earth’s most dynamic environments, shaped by the continuous interplay of natural forces and human activities. These areas are vital for biodiversity, economic activities, and cultural heritage, but they are also highly vulnerable to erosion, sediment displacements, storm inundation, and sea-level rise [1]. Understanding and monitoring the changes in the coastal zone is essential to assess their resilience, plan sustainable management, and mitigate potential risks [2]. Among the various indicators of coastal change, the shoreline plays a central role. As the interface between terrestrial and marine environments, the shoreline reflects the ongoing interactions between land and sea. Its precise monitoring enables researchers and decision makers to track sediment dynamics, assess coastal vulnerability, and develop informed strategies

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to protect these critical areas from the impacts of natural and anthropogenic forces [3]. In this study, the term “shoreline” refers to the “instantaneous” shoreline, namely the land–water boundary as observed at the moment of satellite image acquisition.

Traditional shoreline monitoring methods, such as in situ GNSS surveys and aerial photogrammetry, offer high spatial accuracy but are often labor-intensive, costly, and limited in spatial and temporal coverage. Satellite-based remote sensing, on the contrary, has revolutionized this field, providing repeated observations over large areas at a fraction of the cost [4]. The ability to access archives of historical satellite data further enables a retrospective analysis of shoreline evolution over decades.

Among satellite technologies, multispectral imagery has been widely utilized for shoreline detection, benefiting from a wide range of spatial resolution and the natural contrast between land and water in visible and near-infrared spectra [5]. Medium-resolution images such as Sentinel-2 (S2) from the ESA’s Copernicus program, as well as the Landsat family, have been widely adopted for monitoring large areas and are distributed for free [6]. PLN (CubeSat satellites) provide 3-m spatial resolution images freely accessible for research purposes [7]. Recent studies have demonstrated that using S2 and PLN imagery, an average positional accuracy of around 4 m and 2 m across various dates and microtidal sites can be achieved, respectively [8]. However, multispectral sensors are highly sensitive to atmospheric conditions, with cloud cover and sun glint often limiting their usability, particularly in regions prone to persistent overcast conditions. Moreover, the dependence on solar illumination restricts their ability to collect data at night, leading to temporal gaps in coverage [9].

SAR imagery has emerged as a powerful alternative for environmental studies, overcoming some of the limitations of optical sensors. Operating in the microwave spectrum, SAR systems actively emit signals and measure the backscattered energy, enabling observations regardless of weather or lighting conditions. The unique characteristics of SAR data, such as its sensitivity to surface roughness, dielectric properties, and geometry, make it particularly adapted to delineating the land–water boundary. Sentinel-1 (S1), an ESA C-band SAR mission that provides images at medium spatial resolution (~ 20 m), has been extensively used in different applications in coastal areas such as flooding [10], mangrove, and wetlands monitoring due to its free availability, high frequency of revisits, and consistent coverage. Among SAR platforms, there are options to select paid or on-demand resources such as TerraSAR-X (TSX), which offers higher spatial resolutions (~ 2 m) and operates in the X-band, having been tested in various contexts [11].

Several studies have leveraged SAR data for shoreline extraction. Methodologies range from classical edge-detection methods to advanced ML models. Zollini et al. [12] proposed a semiautomatic methodology for shoreline extraction based on the J-Net Dynamic algorithm to enhance edge detection capabilities and tested it in both SAR and multispectral satellite images in two microtidal beaches. S1 and S2 datasets were coregistered

and preprocessed, with speckle phenomenon reduction filtering applied to the SAR imagery and multispectral indices calculated for the optical one. The resulting data were used to extract shorelines and validate them with GNSS measurements, showing an accuracy for SAR-derived shorelines varying between 1 and 2 S1 pixel sizes. Wu et al. [9] employed DeepLabv3+ for pixel-level semantic segmentation on S1 data, demonstrating robust performance in various coastal environments. Their approach relied on the strong backscatter contrast between land and sea, attributed to differences in surface roughness and dielectric properties. Their best model obtained 0.9 S1 pixel accuracy in a coarser material beach. Other researchers investigated the roles of tidal variation, meteorological conditions, and scene geometry in the accuracy of S1-derived shorelines [13]. Shoreline vectors were derived through segmentation algorithms and validated against high-resolution ground-truth datasets. Temporal variability within tidally influenced environments was analyzed to assess the robustness of the methodology across different geomorphological settings [13]. The effectiveness and potential of utilizing a deep learning solution for identifying and extracting coastlines from satellite SAR images was also investigated by Passarello et al. [14]. Other studies explored the role of polarization and incident angle in optimizing the detection of land–sea boundaries. In particular, Wu et al. [15] found that HH polarization provided the strongest contrast between land and sea surfaces, while incident angles between 30° and 50° were identified as the most effective for accurate shoreline delineation. Kim et al. [16] investigated the role of different radar wavelengths in mapping intertidal areas. They suggested that shorter wavelengths are more useful in mapping low-slope beaches due to the Bragg waves resonant effect. Finally, some studies examined the influence of grain size variations on the backscatter signal captured by SAR sensors [17]. Fine-grained beaches, characterized by smoother surfaces, were associated with lower backscatter intensity, whereas coarse-grained beaches exhibited stronger backscatter due to increased surface roughness. From a methodological point of view, Mao and Splinter [18] endeavored to integrate the capabilities of S1 SAR imagery with Landsat multispectral imagery. Specifically, they addressed a scenario where suitable multispectral images were unavailable due to cloud cover by reconstructing a synthetic modified normalized difference water index. This reconstruction was achieved by training a neural network using S1 SAR imagery data from those specific dates.

Although numerous techniques have been developed for shoreline extraction using SAR imagery, the extent to which the signal from the sea surface differs from that of the adjacent land is not fully understood. This disparity is critical for detecting the land–sea boundary and is influenced by factors such as polarization, land morphology, and sea surface conditions. Polarization affects backscatter strength and contrast, whereas land morphology, including cliffs or dunes, can create shadows or reflections. Meteorological conditions, such as waves and wind, significantly impact SAR backscattering, creating different wavelength undulations on the sea surface and reducing the difference between land and sea. In addition, SAR imagery is affected by the speckle phenomenon, which adds a grainy

appearance and complicates interpretation compared to optical data. Currently, the best accuracy potentially obtained with SAR-derived shorelines (between 10 and 15 m) limits their usability to monitor coastal changes in many beaches.

Motivated by these challenges, this study aims to improve the accuracy of SAR-derived shorelines by addressing the factors contributing to inaccuracies in shoreline extraction. Specifically, we investigate key factors influencing the difference in backscatter response between land and sea pixels in SAR images.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Four Mediterranean beaches—two sandy beaches and two gravel beaches—were selected as study areas (Section II, which also includes the dataset). Reference shorelines from high-resolution aerial orthomosaics and PLN satellite imagery were manually digitized, enabling the quantitative validation of SAR-derived shorelines. For each validation date, the nearest SAR images in ASC and DESC modes were analyzed. Section III presents the methodology. Our approach adapts the shoreline extraction methodology developed by Angelini et al. [19] for optical imagery to SAR data to provide more reliable SAR-extracted shorelines. In addition to standard SAR preprocessing, extra-denoising techniques were tested. The methodology incorporated different polarizations and indices from two radar platforms: S1 (C-band) and TSX (X-band). Clustering methods, such as GMM and k-means, as well as a thresholding technique such as Otsu's [20], were employed to separate land and water. Two additional filtering algorithms, local outlier factor (LOF) and Z-score, were also tested to remove outliers. Section IV presents the results for S1 and TSX, while Section V examines the influence of beach characteristics (sand, dunes, and pebbles), sea state (wave height and wind direction), and satellite orbit. Finally, Section VI concludes this article.

II. STUDY SITES AND DATA COLLECTION

A. Study Sites

The research was carried out on four beaches within the Mediterranean basin, one in Italy and three in Spain [see Fig. 1(a)]. FNG beach (IT) and the SLD (ES) are sandy beaches, while MRJ (ES) and RDC (ES) are pebble beaches. The selection was motivated by the aim of including a variety of grain sizes to evaluate their impact on the SAR capabilities for shoreline detection. In the pictures of Fig. 1(b), the grain size difference between the two sandy beaches (SLD and FNG) and the two gravel beaches (MRJ and RDC) can be visualized. The four sites are located in the western Mediterranean Basin and experience comparable wave and tidal conditions. Tidal fluctuations are minimal, averaging approximately 20 cm, with prolonged periods of calm seas occasionally disrupted by short and intense storms with relatively limited fetch.

FNG beach is part of a natural beach/dune ridge system enclosing the Orbetello lagoon, extending 6 km and anchored landward by the Ansedonia promontory. The beach is composed by fine sand (detailed grain size data are unavailable). The beach faces approximately to the south direction and is exposed to waves primarily from the SE and S directions waves, while SW

Fig. 1. (a) Study area locations and (b) pictures of Feniglia beach (FNG, Italy) (top left), Southern Llobregat Delta (SLD, Spain) (top right), Playa del Marjal (MRJ, Spain) (bottom right), and Ribera de Cabanes (RDC, Spain) (bottom left). The coordinate reference system is WGS84.

waves primarily impact its eastern sector due to sheltering by Monte Argentario [21].

The studied stretch in the SLD spans 10 km along the coast and includes the beaches of Castelldefels, Gavà, and Viladecans cities. This semianthropized coast shows a variable beach width backed by hard structures and composed primarily of sand with a median grain size of $270 \mu\text{m}$. Wave energy predominantly originates from two directions, E-SE and S-SW, with average mean directions of 100° and 176° (from the north), respectively [22].

MRJ is a gravel beach located south of the Ebro Delta, facing the town of Alcanar. It stretches approximately 3 km in length with an average width of 30 m, situated in a semiurban environment. The beach has a mean orientation of 241° relative to the north.

RDC gravel beach is located north of Castelló de la Plana and extends approximately 8 km with a primary orientation of 35° relative to the north. It is a barrier beach that exhibits a berm morphology characterized by a low height and width, with a steep slope facing the sea and a gentler gradient toward the continent. The wave energy in this area is generally low, with 96% of recorded wave heights being less than 2 m [23]. The most energetic waves come from the NE and ENE directions, which are common during autumn and winter [24].

B. Shoreline Reference Data

To validate the analysis, manually digitized instantaneous shorelines from orthomosaics and Planet (PLN) imagery were used as reference data across the study sites. For SLD, only PLN imagery was used (see Fig. 2). Although the spatial resolution of 3 m is lower than that of orthomosaics, PLN offers near-daily coverage, enabling the selection of imagery closely aligned with the SAR data acquisition dates, which consisted of both S1 and TSX platforms. For FNG, orthomosaics were downloaded from the Tuscany region service, GEOscopio WMS.

Fig. 2. Acquisition date of the reference products, either aerial orthophotos (REF-Ortho) or high-resolution PLN images (REF-PLN), used to validate satellite-derived shorelines, and the corresponding S1 (in ASC or DESC mode) and TSX imagery dates at the four sites (from the top SLD, FNG, MRJ, and RDC).

Two orthomosaics from 2019 and 2021, corresponding to the operational period of the S1 mission, were selected (see Fig. 2). These open-access products provide a spatial resolution of 20 cm per pixel. For MRJ, orthophotos from the Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya from 2016 and 2021 were employed, featuring three bands and a 25-cm per pixel resolution (see Fig. 2). For RDC, orthomosaics were sourced from the Institut Cartogràfic Valencià, with datasets available for 2019 and 2022. These products include three bands with a spatial resolution of 25 cm per pixel (see Fig. 2).

The manual digitization of instantaneous shorelines was performed using GIS software. Shoreline positions were identified at the midpoint of the swash zone, corresponding approximately to the intermediate position between wave runup and rundown.

C. SAR Images

Data from S1 and TSX platforms were used in this work. S1 is a radar imaging mission within the European Copernicus program. The mission consists of two satellites, Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B, operating in C-band (5.405 GHz of central frequency) and orbiting in a sun-synchronous configuration with a 180° phase shift. This setup enables a revisit time of 6 days at the Equator in a full operating condition. The S1 radar

operates in four exclusive acquisition modes: Stripmap (SM), interferometric wide swath (IW), extra wide swath (EW), and wave (WV) [25]. The IW mode used in this study provides a spatial resolution of 20×22 m and a swath width of 250 km. Data are delivered as Level-1 ground range detected (GRD) products, which are radiometrically calibrated, georeferenced, and finally distributed with a 10-m pixel spacing [26]. The S1 images are freely available and can be accessed through the ESA Copernicus Browser.

TSX, launched by the German Aerospace Center (DLR), is an X-band radar satellite. It operates at a central frequency of 9.65 GHz and offers a range of imaging modes, including Spotlight, SM, and ScanSAR, with resolutions varying from 1 m to 40 m depending on the mode. The satellite is equipped with flexible imaging geometry, allowing the selection of polarization modes (single, dual, or quad) to suit specific applications. TSX orbits in a sun-synchronous path with a repeat cycle of 11 days. However, interferometric acquisitions can be achieved with a revisit time of less than 24 h when paired with its twin satellite, TanDEM-X. TSX data are provided as Single Look Slant Range Complex or Multi-look GRD products. Comprehensive TSX data are distributed by ESA with an approved project proposal or by commercial vendors.

In this study, the S1 IW GRD SAR images were downloaded free of charge from the Copernicus Browser.¹ The approach consisted of downloading, for each validation date, the pair of images in ASC and DESC mode closest to that date. The TSX dataset was provided by Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA, Barcelona, Spain) and consists of two X-Band images acquired with the SM mode in ASC orbit, with HH polarization, covering the SLD area with a pixel size of $1.4 \text{ m} \times 1.9 \text{ m}$.

D. Wave, Tide, and Wind Data

The shoreline position exhibits significant intrinsic hourly variability influenced by fluctuations in sea level and wave conditions, which can cause apparent landward or seaward movements due to phenomena such as wave setup or storm surges. Among the coastal stretches analyzed, SLD and FNG feature low beach slopes, making them more susceptible to such variations. Conversely, the gravel beaches, RDC and MRJ, have steeper slopes, which mitigate these effects, reducing the tide- and wave-induced migration of the shoreline. For these reasons, a quantitative evaluation of the effect of wave and sea-level variability was only conducted on the two sandy beaches. The potential contribution of changes in setup and mean sea level to shoreline advancement or retreat was assessed by calculating the height difference in sea level at the shoreline (including wave setup) between the date of the satellite imagery and the date of the reference shoreline, divided by the beach slope, following the methodology used by Angelini et al. [27]. To quantify the setup, the formulation proposed by Stockdon et al. [28] was applied. Moreover, at the four beaches, an assessment of the

¹ [Online]. Available: <https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu/>, accessed on 21 December 2024

Fig. 3. Workflow of the SAR shoreline extraction tool. Parallel boxes indicate alternative options.

wave height at the acquisition moment was performed to verify the influence on enhancing the speckle effect on SAR images. In addition, wind was analyzed across all study sites as a potential noise source in SAR images since it can particularly impact the sea surface and complicate land–sea boundary delineation. Sedimentary beaches are also subject to erosion and deposition processes, which can modify the shoreline position during storms. However, we also checked that no significant storms occurred between the reference and the satellite dates.

The wave conditions were obtained from the Giannutri Buoy for FNG beach (Servizio Idrologico Regionale, Tuscany region, Italy), from the Barcelona Buoy II for the SLD coast, and the Tarragona Buoy for MRJ beach (the latter two from Puertos del Estado, Spain). For RDC, data were obtained from the SIMAR virtual buoy number 2087122 (Puertos del Estado). Sea-level data were retrieved from the Civitavecchia Tide Gauge (Italy) for FNG, from the Barcelona 2 tide gauge for SLD, and from the Tarragona tide gauge for MRJ. For RDC, sea-level data were collected from the Mareógrafo de Sagunto. These three latter Spanish tidal gauges are managed by Puertos del Estado. Regarding wind data, measurements for FNG were obtained from the SIR Toscana portal, specifically from the Orbetello weather station. For the Spanish beaches (SLD, MRJ, and RDC), wind data were obtained from the same locations as the respective tide gauges, accessed through the Puertos del Estado portal.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is structured according to the workflow shown in Fig. 3. This workflow is based on the processing of satellite images acquired either from S1 (in both ASC and DESC mode) or from TSX, through a series of steps including preprocessing (see Section III-A), followed by the selection of one image band, one denoising method (see Section III-B), one classification method among those considered (see Section III-C), and finishing with the selection of one of the

outlier detection techniques investigated (see Section III-D). In Fig. 3, parallel boxes represent alternative options. Each step of the workflow is described in detail in the following subsections.

A. Preprocessing SAR Images

The preprocessing of SAR images was performed using the Sentinel application platform version 8.0 [29], distributed by the ESA, and applied to datasets from both S1 IW GRD (ASC and DESC) and TSX satellite images (workflow shown in Fig. 3). A fundamental difference between these datasets lies in their available polarimetric channels, with TSX data relying solely on HH polarization, while S1 imagery includes both VV and VH polarizations. In this work, the S1 VV polarization has been used together with the SAR water index (SARWI), an index proposed by Tian et al. [30], that combines VV, $VH \times VV$, VV^2 , and VH^2 in a weighted-linear relationship.

The first step of the process was the implementation of precise orbit files to refine the satellite’s position and improve geolocation accuracy. Following this, thermal noise removal was applied to mitigate the additive background energy characteristic of radar systems, particularly in the cross-polarization channels, thereby enhancing the quality of the backscatter signal. Subsequently, radiometric calibration was used, transforming raw pixel values into normalized backscatter coefficients, a step essential for ensuring comparability across multiple acquisitions and enabling quantitative interpretation. To address the speckle noise inherent to SAR imagery, a Lee filter [31] was employed with the lowest possible filtering intensity to preserve the spatial resolution and the sharpness of image features. Terrain correction was then performed using the Range-Doppler terrain correction algorithm, incorporating a digital elevation model to correct geometric distortion such as foreshortening and layover, although these effects are not expected with the almost planar topography of the observed areas. After these preprocessing steps, the obtained images were square grids of 10- and 3-m spatial resolution in the S1 and TerraSAR cases, respectively. All data were projected into the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system specific to each area of interest. A geographic subset was extracted to focus the analysis on the coastal regions, optimizing computational efficiency while retaining all relevant spatial information for the subsequent steps of shoreline extraction. Finally, the decibel (dB) scale was used for radar indices.

B. Denoising Techniques

In this study, advanced denoising methodologies were applied to radar images (see Fig. 4). Three methods were considered: Matching and 3-D filtering [BM3D, Fig. 4(b)], total variation denoising [TVD, Fig. 4(c)], and bilateral denoising [BD, Fig. 4(d)]. BM3D operates by grouping similar image blocks into 3-D arrays and applying collaborative filtering in the transform domain. This method excels at denoising by leveraging nonlocal self-similarity [32]. TVD is based on the principle of minimizing the total variation of an image, promoting sparsity in the gradient domain. By penalizing large variations in pixel intensity, this method effectively reduces noise while preserving edges and fine details [33]. BD is a nonlinear filtering approach that combines

Fig. 4. Application of different denoising techniques on the (a) original VVdb image along SLD coast: (b) BM3D, (c) TVD, and (d) BD.

spatial proximity and pixel intensity similarity to smooth images while preserving edges. This dual criterion allows BD to suppress high-frequency noise without compromising the integrity of sharp transitions between regions [34].

These techniques were systematically applied and compared with the outcome of raw SAR imagery to assess their effectiveness in reducing noise, enhancing image interpretability, and improving shoreline detection. The analysis focused on whether the application of these methods could produce a balance between noise reduction and preservation of essential image features, such as the shoreline.

C. Shoreline Detection Algorithm

The methodology for shoreline detection from preprocessed and denoised images (see Fig. 3) was developed as a Python tool, adapting the one developed by Angelini et al. [19]. The procedure started with two raster sources, the preprocessed bands and indices (VVdb and SARWI for S1 and HHdb for TSX). To separate pixels into land and sea classes, three alternative methods were used: one based on automatic threshold definition and the other two on unsupervised ML. These methods were applied independently to the images processed by the three denoising techniques, as well as to the original images, resulting in 24 combinations for S1 and 12 combinations for TSX.

The thresholding method applied in this study was the multithreshold Otsu algorithm [35], an extension of the classic Otsu method. This approach determines multiple thresholds by analyzing the histogram of the input raster and segmenting the image into multiple classes that maximize interclass variance. By introducing additional thresholds, this method offers greater flexibility in handling complex distributions of pixel intensities.

The two unsupervised clustering methods employed K-means or GMM. The K-means algorithm [36] utilizes an approach to partition the image into clusters by minimizing the variance

within each cluster. This method is computationally efficient and well-suited for handling radar images with relatively homogeneous regions. In contrast, GMM [37] adopts a probabilistic framework, modeling the pixel intensity distribution as a mixture of Gaussian components. A certain probability of belonging to a specific component is assigned to each pixel, and the final classification is based on the highest likelihood. The iterative nature of the GMM enables it to adaptively refine the boundaries of clusters, providing a robust segmentation solution even in the presence of overlapping intensity distributions.

The classification methods were tested by defining a region of interest around the coastline to exclude nonrelevant parts of the image, such as the anthropic settlements behind the beach. Classification was performed using either two or three classes. When three classes were used, the classified image was semi-automatically reduced to a binarized form. For sandy beaches, the three classes are assumed to represent the water, the dry sand, and the dune/vegetation. Following this rationale, the two classes with the highest average pixel values were merged into one. On the contrary, for gravel beaches, the three clusters are assumed as water, an area of backscattering transition into the sea, and a dry beach. To support this choice, the two classes with the lower average pixel values were merged into one.

The shoreline extraction process from the binarized image was carried out in three different steps. Initially, contours were identified by analyzing the raster data with a marching square algorithm, which applied a threshold of 0.5 to ensure that the extracted line passed centrally through the boundary pixels. Among the generated contours, the one with the longest length was selected to represent the shoreline, as this typically corresponded to the main land–water interface. To enhance the accuracy and smoothness of the resulting line, a Laplacian smoothing algorithm was then employed. This smoothing process relied on two parameters: a smoothing factor of 0.2, which influenced how each point was adjusted based on its neighboring points, and the number of iterations (set to 10), which were used to progressively refine the line shape. The implementation of this smoothing methodology was maintained to ensure consistency with the approach previously developed for multispectral images [19]. However, we previously confirmed that the parameters selected for this first smoothing algorithm did not produce any strong effects capable of altering the subsequent outlier detection phase.

D. Outlier Detection and Validation Process

The nature of radar data entails the presence of Gaussian noise. Despite partially reducing it during the preprocessing and denoising stages, detected shorelines can show errors, sometimes in the form of outliers. To further refine the analysis, two outlier detection filters were tested on the extracted shorelines. The LOF [38] algorithm evaluates the local density of each data point relative to its neighbors, identifying points as outliers when their density is significantly lower than that of the surrounding data. The Z-score approach [39] computes the standard deviation of individual data points from the mean of the dataset, flagging those that exceed a predetermined threshold as outliers.

The specific algorithm employed for outlier detection started with the definition of a mean shoreline, a strongly smoothed version of the detected shoreline. It was retrieved from interpolated points along each shoreline at an interval of 10 m, accordingly with the grid spacing of the images, by applying a moving-window smoothing technique with a window size of 750 m. The window size was selected based on the coastal characteristics of the study sites, as it effectively filters out alongshore shoreline undulations while preserving overall beach curvature. Central finite differences were subsequently used to calculate tangent vectors between the points on the interpolated line. From these, a set of perpendicular transects was generated based on the identified direction. The distance along these directions between the mean line and the extracted shoreline points was used to define LOF and z-score. For the LOF-based outlier detection, we used a number of nearest neighbors equal to 20 and a threshold of 1.5. The first parameter specifies that, for each data point, the local density is estimated by considering its 20 nearest neighbors, and a threshold equal to 1.5 indicates that any data point with an LOF score greater than 1.5 is considered an outlier. These values were chosen to achieve a balance between sensitivity to outliers and robustness to false positives. On the other hand, for the Z-score-based method, a threshold of Z-score equal to 3 was employed, meaning that any observation with a value exceeding 3 standard deviations from the local mean is flagged as an anomaly to exclude only the most extreme anomalies relative to the local shoreline trend.

Validation of the different cases examined, namely the various combinations of indices and methods for shoreline extraction, was performed using the baseline and transect method. For this purpose, a baseline was established along and behind the beaches, and perpendicular lines (transects) were drawn at 10-m intervals relative to the baseline. Each transect intersected both the reference shoreline and the automatically extracted SAR shorelines. The sign used in subsequent calculations was first determined. By convention, a negative (positive) sign was assigned when the extracted shoreline laid landward (seaward) of the reference shoreline. Finally, several statistical indicators of the distance between the two shorelines were computed to assess accuracy and robustness: the MAD and the Bias (or Mean, μ_d) as follows:

$$\text{MAD} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |d_i| \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_d = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i \quad (2)$$

where N is the total number of transects and d_i is the distance for the i th transect.

IV. RESULTS

A. Main Results for S1 Images

A total of two indices (VVdb and SARWI), three denoising methods (BM3D, TVD, and BD) and the original data (RAW)

were tested separately using two unsupervised clustering methods (K-means and GMM) and one thresholding method (Otsu) were analyzed on 20 S1 images when in situ data or orthomosaics were available (see Fig. 2). One automatic thresholding method and two unsupervised classification methods were also employed. The combination of these indices, denoising, and clustering methods resulted in 20 shorelines extracted for each of the ten reference images. An example of one extracted shoreline for each site is shown in Fig. 5. The obtained results, separated by site, are summarized in Fig. 6 in terms of MAD and in Fig. 7 in terms of bias. These MAD and bias correspond to all the transects of all the images of each site, so they allow assessing which combination of methods was able to extract more accurate shorelines in each of the four study areas (SLD, FNG, MRJ, and RDC).

The average results for each site showed a strong regularity in gravel beaches: both MRJ and RDC display the majority of the method combinations below the S1 pixel size threshold in terms of MAD (the light yellow area in Figs. 6 and 7). In particular, the BM3D denoising method proves to be highly effective, pushing accuracy to around 6 m. The bias (see Fig. 7) showed, on average, positive values (seaward) or values close to zero in the gravel beaches. It is worth noting that, in general, the RAW data exhibit higher bias values.

For sandy beaches, however, results were different in the two sites. In FNG, a very good accuracy was obtained, with best MAD values slightly below 5 m (i.e., half of S1 pixel, Fig. 6). At SLD, on the other hand, the shoreline extraction process was more challenging, and the results showed higher variability in terms of MAD and Bias, which will be discussed in Section V-B. Note that the coastal extension was larger in SLD (10 km), and there were more dates tested, some of them with challenging weather conditions. Nevertheless, with the VVdb index, the TVD denoising methodology, and the GMM classification method, it was possible to achieve an accuracy of slightly less than 1 px (10 m) in terms of MAD (see Fig. 6). It is important to note here that the original images collected by S1 have a resolution of ≈ 20 m, making the results obtained even better. In both sandy beaches, the bias generally showed negative values (landward), especially in SLD (see Fig. 7).

B. Main Results for TSX Images

Only two TSX images for the SLD beach were available (first plot from the top in Fig. 2). For TSX, the combinations of HHdb polarization with three denoising methods (BM3D, TVD, and BD) and the original data (RAW) were tested on these two images. Since the three automatic classification methods were also tested, 12 shorelines were detected in each image. An example of the two SAR images and the corresponding derived shorelines for the 2018 date is shown in Fig. 8. The results for the TSX data are summarized in Fig. 9 in terms of MAD and in Fig. 10 in terms of bias.

The results on the two dates showed significant differences in accuracy. The 2017 data obtained a best MAD value of approximately 7.5 m, likely due to the associated meteorological conditions (details in Section V-B). In contrast, the 2018 data

Fig. 5. Examples of SAR-derived shorelines from S1 (green line), compared to the reference one (blue line) on the (a) FNG, (b) MRJ, and (c) RDC stretch of coast.

achieved very high accuracy levels, with the smaller MAD values being of 2.5 m, roughly corresponding to the TSX pixel size (3 m) [see Fig. 9(a)]. On that specific date, with S1 data, an accuracy of 6.5 m was achieved. A test was also conducted on the same two TSX images, but resampling them to the S1 pixel size (10 m) [see Fig. 9(b)]. The best results obtained after resampling were comparable to those using the original resolution TSX images, reaching an accuracy of 2.5 m in terms of MAD, but some combinations gave significantly larger errors.

C. Sensitivity of Shoreline Extraction to Several Methodological Aspects

Among the implemented classification and thresholding methods, no significant sensitivity was observed under favorable weather conditions (cases of FNG, MRJ, and RDC).

In contrast, in more variable situations, such as those observed on SLD beach, GMM and (to a lesser extent) K-means clustering methods outperformed Otsu (smaller MAD in Figs. 6 and 9).

Denosing techniques have been shown to always improve the performance compared to the use of raw data (see Figs. 6 and 9), especially on dates characterized by unfavorable weather and sea conditions in SLD (more details in Section V-B). In particular, in three out of the four examined sites, combinations that incorporate BM3D denosing techniques demonstrated superior performance compared to the other denosing methods. In SLD, results were more variable, and any of the three denosing techniques could give the best result. The implemented denosing techniques play an important role in enhancing the ability to distinguish the boundary between the backscatter values of water and sand.

Fig. 6. MAD obtained for the 24 combinations of index, denoising technique, and classification method at each site (averaged across all dates) for the S1 platform. The three best-performing combinations in terms of MAD are highlighted. The yellow shaded area indicates the pixel size of S1 (10 m). For illustrative purposes, the configuration combining the VVdb index (empty filling), TVD denoising (triangle shape), and GMM classification method (blue color) is shown as the best-performing setup in terms of MAD value at the SLD site.

Fig. 7. Bias obtained for the 24 combinations of index, denoising technique, and classification method at each site (averaged across all dates) for the S1 platform. The three best-performing combinations in terms of bias are highlighted. The yellow shaded area indicates the pixel size of S1 (10 m). For illustrative purposes, the configuration combining the VVdb index (empty filling), TVD denoising (triangle shape), and K-means classification method (red color) is shown as the one achieving the bias value closest to zero at the FNG site.

Regarding the application of outlier detection methods, both tested approaches identified a small percentage of outliers on the SLD coast. On the other hand, in the other coastal stretches, due to the regularity of the extracted lines, no outliers were detected by the algorithm. On average, the LOF detected 1% of

outliers, and the z-score method gave 2% of outliers. Excluding these outliers led to a modest increase in accuracy, with MAD improving by approximately 0.4 m on the 2017 TSX date and 0.5 m on the 2018 TSX date (5% and 15% improvement, respectively). For the S1 analysis, the mean improvement was 0.4 m,

Fig. 8. Examples of SAR-derived shorelines from S1 (DESC) (green line) and TSX (red line), compared to the reference one (blue line) on the SLD stretch of coast in 2018. (a) Extracted shorelines with the S1 image in the background. (b) Extracted shorelines with the TSX image in the background.

corresponding to 4%. This means that on many occasions, the errors on the detected shoreline were not in the form of outliers.

The use of two versus three classes in image classification was also tested in the four beaches. Employing three classes instead of two proved advantageous across all examined cases studied (results with two classes are not shown). The third class in the sandy beaches allowed for better identification of the dry beach by reducing the negative bias when merging the two classes with the higher average backscatter. For gravel beaches, in contrast, merging the two classes with the lowest backscatter reduced the positive bias. MAD experienced a more marked reduction in gravel beaches, approximately 5 m (50 % improvement), and around 5 m in the more variable context of SLD (33 % improvement). In FNG, where the results were already very satisfactory with two classes, the reduction was about 1.5 m (23 % improvement). This analysis was also conducted for the two available dates of the TSX. On the 2017 date, which presented the worst conditions, the improvement was approximately 1 m (12 % improvement). Conversely, on the 2018 date, the improvement was about 0.5 m (16 % improvement). Similar trends were recorded for both the original and resampled data.

Finally, the applied methodology did not account for a shoreline correction related to sea level differences due to tides and wave setup between the image and the reference dates. These displacements were assumed to be small because our research focused on four micro tidal beaches where tidal oscillation is

below 20 cm. To confirm this hypothesis, the contributions of sea level and wave setup to potential shoreline displacements were assessed for the two sandy beaches analyzed, FNG and SLD, as they exhibit a mild swash slope. The gravel beaches have a larger swash slope, which results in an even more limited planimetric displacement of the instantaneous shoreline. The apparent total shoreline displacements due to waves and tides were calculated as described in Section II-D. As shown in Table I, displacements were typically below 2 m in the S1 cases and below 1 m for TSX, so they were significantly smaller than the obtained accuracy.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Role of Grain Size and Radar Wavelength on Backscattering

Radar backscattering is strongly influenced by grain size and SAR wavelength. When the particles are small compared to the wavelength, in the so-called Rayleigh regime, the intensity of the backscattered energy is proportional to the ratio between d^6 and λ^4 , where d is the grain size and λ is the SAR wavelength [40]. This condition applies to the two studied sandy beaches, with $d = 0.27$ mm in SLD and $d = 1$ mm at most in FNG (no measurements are available there), considering both the S1 (center in 5.5 cm) and the TSX (center in 3.1 cm) wavelengths. We do not know the pebble size of two gravel beaches, but the order of magnitude ranges between 1 and 10 cm. In these cases,

Fig. 9. MAD obtained for the 12 combinations of index, denoising technique, and classification method in the SLD site for each of the two dates for the TSX platform. The three best combinations in terms of MAD are highlighted. (a) Results obtained along the two dates with the original pixel size (OR) (3 m) represented by the orange-shaded area. (b) Results obtained along the two dates with resampled TSX data to S1 data pixel size (RES) (10 m). For illustrative purposes: The configuration combining index HHdb (empty filling), BD denoising (circle shape), and K-means classification method (red color) is shown as the best-performing setup in terms of MAD value on 1017 OR.

Fig. 10. Bias obtained for the 12 combinations of index, denoising technique, and classification method in the SLD site for each of the two dates for the TSX platform. The three best combinations in terms of Bias are highlighted. (a) Results obtained along the two dates with the original pixel size (OR) (3 m) represented by the orange-shaded area. (b) Results obtained along the two dates with resampled TSX data to S1 data pixel size (RES) (10 m). For illustrative purposes: The configuration combining index HHdb (empty filling), BD denoising (circle shape), and GMM classification method (blue color) is shown as the one achieving the bias value closest to zero on 1017 OR.

Fig. 11. Box plots of the backscatter values of land and sea averaged over the available dates, for each site and platform. A mask around the reference line was used to select pixel values on the exposed beach portion (LAND) and the equivalent number of pixels in the sea (SEA). SLD and FNG are sandy beaches (gold color), while MRJ and RDC are gravel beaches (light gray).

TABLE I
PLANIMETRIC SHORELINE DISPLACEMENTS DUE TO BOTH TIDAL AND WAVE
SETUP CONTRIBUTIONS

Reference Shoreline Date	Total distance (m) S1 (ASC) Reference	Total distance (m) S1 (DESC) Reference	Total distance (m) TSX Reference
SLD (Barcelona 2 tide gauge/ Barcelona buoy II)			
26/10/2017	0.8	-1.5	-0.8
19/05/2018	-0.1	-0.5	0.4
24/05/2023	0.1	0.8	–
04/06/2023	1.3	1.2	–
FNG (Civitavecchia harbor/Giannutri buoy)			
19/07/2019	-1.4	-0.3	–
20/07/2021	1.7	2.1	–

The apparent total distances are between the S1 (both ASC and DESC images) and the TSX-derived shorelines and the reference ones. The positions of the tide gauges/buoys used for the analyses are reported in Section II-D for the two coastal areas. The difference in days between S1 and TSX to the reference are shown in Fig. 2.

where the grain size is comparable to or larger than the SAR wavelength, the response moves to the Mie and optical regime, resulting in a more complex response.

The S1 results obtained in our study were generally better for the gravel beaches, which showed a very good accuracy of half a pixel and a small dispersion of MAD values across different methods. A possible explanation is the higher backscatter from the exposed gravel beach with larger grain sizes compared to the sandy beach for the same wavelength. In Fig. 11, the backscatter intensity (in dB) of the VV polarization of S1 and for HH

polarization of TSX, averaged over all dates for each site, is shown. To collect the backscatter data from the emerged part of the beach (LAND in Fig. 11), an appropriate mask was created based on the reference line of each date for each site, ensuring that no other landward features were included. A mirrored mask was created to collect an equal number of backscatter values seaward (SEA in Fig. 11). The test shows that, in general, sandy beaches (SLD and FNG) tend to exhibit lower land backscatter values on average. Gravel beaches (MRJ and RDC), on the other hand, show higher land backscatter responses, which also influence the data collected in the sea portion. This also explains the slight seaward bias observed in the results of gravel beaches. In general, a greater separation between sea and land backscatter is observed on the gravel beaches and in FNG compared to SLD (S1). In this latter site, more acquisition dates were available and some of them were affected by unfavorable weather conditions (see the next section).

Several studies have investigated the effects of using different SAR platforms with varying wavelengths for shoreline detection. For example, Wu et al. [15] showed that X-band SAR may be preferred over L-band SAR (peak wavelength in 20 cm) for shoreline detection, especially in areas where the beach material consists of finer grains. In our study, the TSX satellite platform operating in the X-band (peak wavelength in 3.1 cm) was compared with the S1 platform in the C-band (peak in 5.5 cm) in SLD. The comparison was conducted on the two available dates for TSX, selecting the closest S1 images, and with both dates close to the reference one (2). In addition, both the original TSX data at a 3-m per pixel resolution and a resampled version at 10-m per pixel, matching the S1 resolution, were considered in the analysis to separate the effect of the better spatial resolution of the X-band platform from that of the smaller wavelength (9).

The comparison in SLD, characterized by fine sand, revealed an advantage in utilizing TSX over S1, with errors decreasing from 6.5 m in the former (best method combination) to 2.5 m in the 2018 date. This is coherent with Fig. 9, showing that, in SLD, TSX data show a greater difference in backscatter values between the land and sea pixels than S1 data. In 2017 date, the improvement was not relevant, probably due to the occurrence of other sources of error (see Section V-B). The use of TSX images resampled to S1 resolution also demonstrated the potential to achieve an accuracy comparable to that of the original TSX spatial resolution on the two available dates Section IV-B. This indicates that accuracy is more influenced by the wavelength relative to surface roughness rather than by spatial resolution. Further investigations are warranted, primarily by employing a greater number of dates.

B. Role of Meteorological Conditions on Backscattering

Meteorological conditions (waves and wind) can not only produce an apparent migration of the instantaneous shoreline (see Section IV-C), but also contribute to increasing the sea clutter signal in SAR imagery and can potentially impact the four sites. The conditions providing the highest contrast between land and water in SAR backscattering are generally accepted to be a smooth sea surface (relative to the wavelength corresponding to the radar frequency), in which case pixels associated with the sea are black (corresponding to the minimum value of the radar signal, i.e., only noise). In such ideal conditions, pixels associated with the beach border are stable, without significant deep and foam, thus providing a high contrast. When the sea surface becomes rough due to waves and wind, its backscattering response increases, reducing the contrast between sand and water pixels. The sea can even reach high values when the Bragg scattering conditions are related to sea surface undulations, wavelength, and incidence angle of the radar signal. The role of the interference of radar signal with wavelength and height of sea waves can even introduce a bias in coastline retrieval [41]. Many researchers have investigated how wind, waves, and tides influence the increase of the speckle phenomenon in radar data. For example, Wu et al. [15] showed how backscattering was affected by wave heights greater than 0.5 m. Local winds, such as breezes, can also generate local waves of a wavelength that can obscure shoreline detection [41].

A quantification of this aspect was conducted for the S1 images of SLD beach, given the variability of conditions experienced across the larger number of dates considered (see Fig. 2). The correlation coefficient between the MAD of each date and the wind speed and wave data was evaluated with Pearson's coefficient first using the raw images and then the denoised images. A significant correlation between MAD and wind speed for RAW images ($r = 0.64$) was found while wave height appeared less correlated with MAD ($r = 0.34$), as shown in Fig. 12(a). A significant error reduction was observed with the use of denoising techniques, particularly on dates most affected by adverse meteorological and marine conditions [see Fig. 12(b)]. Denoised data showed a low correlation between MAD and both wind ($r = 0.16$) and waves ($r = 0.4$) on the same dates.

Fig. 12. Relationship between MAD, wind speed, and wave height. (a) Result of combining GMM clustering on VVdb polarization using RAW data (i.e., without denoising). (b) Result of combining GMM clustering on VVdb polarization using TVD denoising. The size of the circles increases with the MAD, following the color scale from purple to yellow.

Regarding the TSX–S1 comparison in SLD, the TSX data from 2017 was acquired under more unfavorable wind conditions (5 m/s) compared to the corresponding S1 data (3.2 m/s). This may explain why using the TSX image did not improve the accuracy in this case. By contrast, in the 2018 dates, under similar wind conditions—2.6 m/s for the TSX acquisition and 2.9 m/s for the S1 image—the shoreline extraction accuracy, in terms of MAD, was 2.5 m for TSX and 6.5 m for S1.

Finally, beaches with a wide intertidal zone are additionally affected by changes in soil moisture. The episodic beach inundation can drastically vary the dielectric properties of the sand, and SAR backscattering could likely experience a more significant change in the wet-dry sand transition rather than in the sea-wet beach boundary [13]. In this study, this might explain why the bias was slightly negative for FNG and strongly negative for SLD (see Fig. 7), meaning that the detected shorelines were located landward of the reference ones. In particular, the latter site experienced worse meteorological conditions on some of the examined dates, which might create more inundation moments that accentuate this effect. Contrarily, in gravel beaches, the strong backscattering produced by the pebbles, together with the lack of wet sand, shifted the boundary of the land class toward the sea (see Fig. 7). This phenomenon was particularly evident in the results of the RAW data.

C. Influence of Orbits on Shoreline Detection

According to previous studies, the direction of observation (sea-shore or land-sea) can significantly influence the quality of shoreline extraction. ASC and DESC orbits determine different observation geometries, which in turn influence SAR backscatter and shoreline delineation [15]. In our study, we calculated the angles formed between the average orientation of the examined beaches and the direction of the different ASC or DESC orbit line of sight. SLD and FNG, with similar E-W orientations (85° and 111° relative to the North, respectively), exhibited little distinction between ASC and DESC orbits in terms of beach perspective. The situation was slightly different for MRJ and RDC (61° and 35° relative to the North, respectively). However, no patterns were observed in the results concerning the orbit either.

Another investigated factor is the incidence angle between the sensor's outgoing signal and the terrain, but no influence was found on the results. The examined beaches all fell within a range of incidence angles between 30° and 50° , which is optimal for avoiding negative effects in shoreline detection [15].

D. Strengths and Limitations of the Applied Methodologies

Previous studies on shoreline extraction from SAR images had employed both probabilistic validation approaches [13], [15] and methods utilizing in situ data [12], [42], achieving accuracies ranging between 10 and 15 m (larger than the S1 pixel size). By employing denoising methodologies, various clustering techniques, and outlier filters, our work has advanced the reliability and accuracy of shorelines extracted from SAR imagery, with unprecedented accuracies up to 5 m (half of S1 pixel size).

Compared to some probabilistic approaches, our methodology is limited by the reduced number of images utilized. The number of S1 images tested was large enough to produce a robust outcome, but the obtained TSX results should be confirmed by testing on more images. In addition, the methodology was tested on beaches with different geomorphological characteristics, but all located within the Mediterranean basin under microtidal conditions and on dates with near-ideal weather conditions. The methodology could be applied globally, testing it in the future in beaches with significant tides, especially because the results obtained in this study using clustering methods with multiple classes in sandy beaches suggest the possibility of identifying the intertidal zone in tidal environments, based on the varying backscattering on the water, the wet low-lying sand area, and the dry sand area.

In instances of adverse meteorological conditions and in environments characterized by fine, flood-prone sands (SLD site), the accuracies achieved have been variable, but they represent an improvement on previous studies. Restricting the use of SAR data to favorable weather conditions (e.g., wave height < 0.5 m and wind speed < 3 m/s) would provide more accurate results (of 5 m in this study), but this would diminish image availability and thereby SAR advantages over optical data, particularly regarding nocturnal operability. The application of denoising techniques

appears to partially decouple accuracy from meteorological conditions (see Fig. 12), thereby increasing usability.

A potential limitation arises from the use of PLN data as a reference in the case of SLD. Given the availability of TSX data on only two specific dates, the authors were compelled to use a manually digitized reference from PLN, which provides near-daily imagery. Considering that manual digitization entails an error comparable to the PLN pixel size (3 m), the accuracy is close to the MAD values found for the TSX images in the best case.

A notable strength of our approach is that it did not require substantial efforts to transition from the methodology developed by Angelini et al. [19] for multispectral images to SAR images. The only changes involved the preprocessing module and the identification of outliers. Compared to shoreline extraction results obtained from optical data, which typically report accuracies of around 4–5 m using 10-m resolution imagery in microtidal environments [19], [43], shoreline detection from radar data generally achieves slightly lower accuracy. The methodology developed in this study helps narrow this gap, facilitating a potential fusion of SAR and multispectral images in subsequent works.

The successful application of the X-band SAR images (TSX) in sandy beach areas, particularly challenging from a conservation perspective, suggests the potential of using other X-band platforms, such as the Spanish PAZ or the Italian COSMO-SkyMed. Future work should involve expanding the available X-band image dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, the potential of SAR imagery for automatic shoreline detection has been evaluated by applying a combination of SAR polarizations, denoising techniques, clustering or thresholding methods, and outlier detection filters. Shorelines extracted from 20 S1 and two TSX images have been validated against high-resolution reference datasets obtained from aerial orthomosaics and PLN imagery. Four Mediterranean beaches characterized by different grain sizes and geomorphological settings have been studied.

SAR-based shoreline extraction significantly improves when applying denoising techniques, particularly the BM3D filter, which consistently reduces noise and enhances the clarity of the land-sea boundary. The use of three clusters (instead of two) in the classification algorithm also improves the results, but the addition of an outlier detection method only implies a marginal decrease in errors. With all these improvements, an unprecedented subpixel accuracy is achieved in terms of MAD, both in gravel (6 m) and in sandy (7 m) beaches (significantly below the pixel size of S1). At one of the sandy coasts, both S1 and TSX images have been used on two dates. On one date, the best-performing configurations provide an MAD of approximately 6.5 m for S1 and around 2.5 m for TSX, demonstrating that X-band data can yield higher accuracy than C-band data, especially in environments with fine sand. However, further investigation should be performed because S1 and TSX give

similar accuracies (7 m) on the other date, probably due to worse conditions on the TSX image time acquisition.

In general, errors in shoreline detection are smaller if backscatter values between land and sea differ more, which happens for gravel beaches and the sandy site with better accuracy. The influence of meteorological conditions has also been analyzed, and a significant negative correlation between wind speed and shoreline accuracy is observed, while wave height seems to have a smaller impact. Denoising filters are effective in mitigating these meteorological effects, particularly for S1 data. Contrarily, the comparison between ASC and DESC orbits does not reveal systematic differences in shoreline accuracy across the study sites, although previous studies suggested that the geometry of SAR acquisition can affect detection performance.

This study highlights the strengths and limitations of SAR-based shoreline detection. In general, the methodology proves effective in extracting accurate and reliable shorelines, particularly in the two gravel beaches and one of the sandy sites. Thereby, SAR imagery could indeed serve as a viable alternative to optical data, especially under cloudy conditions or during nighttime acquisitions. However, its performance can be affected by surface roughness and environmental conditions. Future research should focus on extending this analysis to a broader range of coastal environments, including meso and macrotidal areas, to further refine the methodology and assess its applicability under more variable meteorological conditions.

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Data availability: The codes and data supporting all results shown in the manuscript are available from the corresponding authors upon request.

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